

Studies on Development of Fuel Briquettes using Biodegradable Waste Materials

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ABSTRACT

To cater the increased needs of humans, energy being crucial, has left no choice for researchers to work on alternative fuels like nuclear energy etc. Despite of its pollution and un-safety, nuclear energy is cost well established. Hence an attempt is made to prepare fuel briquettes from locally available waste materials as alternative sources of energy production. The briquettes were evaluated for the following properties: moisture, ash, volatile matter, fixed carbon, sulfur, calorific value, combustion calorific value, compressive strength, and water resistance. The experimental results indicated that calorific value and combustion calorific value of the solid fuel briquettes more in coconut coir. The results indicate that rice husk briquettes have more moisture content, paper briquette has more ash content and coconut coir has high volatile matter content and fixed carbon content by using a muffle furnace. The apparent water absorption is more for paper briquette. From the experimental properties of solid fuel briquettes produced from rejected material of paper, rice husk and coconut coir. The percentages of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen for paper are 51.12%, 5.038%, 1.9832%, 0.203%, 49.8382% respectively. The percentages of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen for rice husk are 43.052%, 4.0357%, 1.1254%, 0.254%, 38.159% respectively. The percentages of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen for 52.012%, 5.057%, 0.9200%, 0.172%, 52.067% respectively.

Keyword: Fuel Briquettes, Proximate Analysis, Ultimate Analysis, FTIR, XRD, SEM.

INTRODUCTION

Briquetting is the process of conversion of agricultural waste into uniformly shaped briquettes that are easy to use, transport and store. The briquetting of biomass improves its handling characteristics, increase the volumetric calorific value, reduces transportation costs and makes it available for a variety of application. Briquettes were discovered to be an important source of energy during the first and second world wars for heat and electricity production using simple technologies. Briquette charcoal is viewed as an advanced fuel because of its clean burning nature and the fact it can be stored for long periods of time without degradation. Hence this study focused on providing biomass as an alternative to wood charcoal using locally abundant agricultural wastes converted into charcoal briquettes on a small scale.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fuel briquettes can be made from readily available waste materials. In urban areas, this can be sawdust and

shredded paper. In villages and rural areas, they can be made from leaves, grass, coffee and rice husks and other agricultural waste in many combinations. Waste plastic material cannot be used because the plastic gives off toxic gases when it burns. Green raw materials like leaves and grass are moistened and partially decomposed under black plastic for several days, then dried and pounded or chopped into small pieces about the size of cornflakes. Annual production of cotton or rough textile fibers wastes of one cotton mill ranges from 10 to 200 tons. Usually the waste is stored in the municipal refuse depots in form of blended waste. Increasing of the cotton yarn production results in high amount of waste originated during cotton processing and therefore there are searched ways how that waste could be used. India, as we all know is the second biggest sugarcane growing country in the World, only behind Brazil. Every year, 4 million hectares had been planted with sugarcane. Sugar plant can process 40 million tons sugarcane every year. For each ton of sugarcane crushed, about 300 kg of bagasse is

retrieved. Previously bagasse is used as the fuel of sugar production. However only a third of bagasse are flamed, the remaining is discarded. That is to say, making bagasse into briquettes contains huge potential.

Collecting wastes and preparing them: All the wastes are firstly cleaned out thoroughly with water to remove dirt and are dried on open top for 15 days. Primary Samples are ready after they are completely dried out. The dried samples were cut into small pieces (about ½ inch). The samples were soaked in 3 different buckets for 24 hours. After 24 hrs. the samples were filtered using a mesh and partially dried for 15 min.

Preparation of Binder: The binder we have taken is maida (wheat flour). The amount of binder should be added is known while making trails. We found about 100 gms of maida prepared will be sufficient. In the hot water maida flour is added slowly and stirred vigorously and continuously. Checked once that there are no lumps formed. Binder will attain the sticky nature. maida gives good strength to the samples and thus prevents them from collapsing during firing.

Preparing Briquetting sample: The water filtered sample is then mixed with the binder. Both are mixed well. Then the mixture is kept into mould which is placed on a wooden plank. After putting all the prepared mixture the mould is closed with lid and kept under fitted bench vise and tightened to apply pressure. The pressure is applied for about 24 hours.

Drying: After 24 hrs. the mould should be carefully removed. A rectangular briquette with high moisture content is obtained. Then it should be dried enough to obtain a rigid briquette. During drying, the maida (plain flour), which would have formed a layer over the particles, changes from a semi-solid to a solid form, thus holding the particles together.

Firing of the samples: The samples were fired in an electrically heated muffle furnace. The muffle furnace is a box like receptacle usually made of fire clay or another refractory material. The muffle is so place in the furnace that all sides except the front are heated. There is generous vent of rectangular shape in the back of the muffle the refractory vessels containing the sample are placed in the muffle, and there is no direct contact with the fuel or its products of combustion. The muffle furnace which we used has temperature range from 00c to 12000c and in our present study we observed their properties at 7000c, 8000c and 9000c. The samples were heated according to the following firing schedule. They were heated from room temperature to 1000C. The temperature was then raised to 2500C at a rate of 20C/min. From 2500C the 3500C at 10C/min. Subsequent heating was carried out at 20C/min up to 9000C. The samples were then kept at the final temperature for 2 hours before they were allowed to slowly cool down to room temperature in the furnace.

RESULT

CHARACTERIZATION OF BRIQUETTE MATERIAL XRD

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is an analytical technique looking at X-ray scattering from crystalline materials. Each material produces a unique X-ray "fingerprint" of X-ray intensity versus scattering angle that is characteristic of its

crystalline atomic structure. Qualitative analysis is possible by comparing the XRD pattern of an unknown material to a library of known patterns.

In x-ray diffraction work we normally distinguish between single crystal and polycrystalline or powder applications. The single crystal sample is a perfect (all unit cells aligned in a perfect extended pattern) crystal with a cross section of about 0.3 mm. The single crystal diffractometer and associated computer package is used mainly to elucidate the molecular structure of novel compounds, either natural products or manmade molecules. Powder diffraction is mainly used for "finger print identification" of various solid materials, e.g. asbestos, quartz. In powder or polycrystalline diffraction it is important to have a sample with a smooth plane surface. If possible, we normally grind the sample down to particles of about 0.002 mm to 0.005 mm cross section. The ideal sample is homogeneous and the crystallites are randomly distributed (we will later point out problems which will occur if the specimen deviates from this ideal state). The sample is pressed into a sample holder so that we have a smooth flat surface. Ideally we now have a random distribution of all possible h, k, l planes. Only crystallites having reflecting planes (h, k, l) parallel to the specimen surface will contribute to the reflected intensities. If we have a truly random sample, each possible reflection from a given set of h, k, l planes will have an equal number of crystallites contributing to it. We only have to rock the sample through the glancing angle THETA in order to produce all possible reflections. The xrd analysis results for coconut paper, rice husk and coconut coir are given below:

Fig 1 (a) XRD Pattern Of paper Sample Fuel Briquette

Fig 1 (b) XRD Pattern Of paper Sample Fuel Briquette-Matching Compounds

The powder XRD patterns for the starting raw material of paper is manifested in Fig.

1.(a, b).the minerals identified for paper are Khademite [Al(SO₄F 5H₂O)], Calcium Catena Polyphosphate[Ca(PO₃)₂] and Monodic Titanium Phosphate[Ba₃TiV₄Oi₅], Ytterbium polysulfide[S11.048 Y6] Goodness-of-fit parameter for observed reflections is 2.1. Ambient diffraction temperature 295 K. Terbium phosphate[TbPO₄] Under the identical synthetic conditions, the crystal structure of the TbPO₄ products have been identified by XRD analysis. XRD pattern of the TbPO₄ nanorods at pH =2. All diffraction peaks agree well with a hexagonal structure of TbPO₄ • H₂O (PDF card no 20-1244). The XRD patterns of TbPO₄ products with different pH values (pH = 1, 2, 6 and 10) are characteristic of a pure hexagonal phase of terbium phosphate hydrate. Tridymite[SiO₂] axial rotations are a:b:c =0.5769:1:4.7551. its xrd is by Intensity(I/Io): 4.107(1), 4.328(0.9), 3.818(0.5), aluminium phosphate[H₃AlO₄P] compound is also matched with this briquette. RICEHUSK

Fig 2 (a) XRD Pattern Of Rice husk Sample Fuel Briquette

Fig 2 (b) XRD Pattern Of Rice husk Sample Fuel Briquette-Matching Compounds

The powder XRD patterns for the starting raw material of rice husk is manifested in Fig. 2(b), the minerals identified for paper are Althupite [ThAl (UO₂)₇(PO₄)₄(OH)₅ 15(H₂O)], Melanophosphate [SiO₂ n(C₁H₁O₁S)] and Halotrichite [FeAl₂(SO₄) 22FH₂O]. X Ray Diffraction: 3.5(1), 4.3(1), 4.81(1), Forms: (1 3 1) (1 1 0) (1 1 1).

Cesium sodium uranyl peroxide hydroxide [Cs₈ Na_{17.76} O₂₉₄ U₃₄] has diffraction radiation wavelength 0.71073 Å

The powder XRD patterns for the starting raw material of paper is manifested in fig. The minerals identified for paper are Cesium-tantalum-Sulfide [CS₂TaS₂], Goodness-of-fit parameter for observed reflections 1.065. Diffraction radiation

wavelength 0.71073 Å. Quenstedtite [Fe₃+2(SO₄) 10H₂O], Crystal System: Triclinic – Pinacoidal H-M Symbol (1) Space Group: P1. X Ray Diffraction: By Intensity(I/Io): 4.109(1), 4.217(0.87), 5.837(0.66) Forms: (0 1 0) (1 1 0) (1 2 0) (0 3 1) (0 2 1) (0 1 1) (1 0 0) and Rubidium Uranyl Borate[Rd₂[(UO₂)₂B₁₃O₂₀(OH)₅] Coconut coir

Fig 3 (a) XRD Pattern Of Coconut coir Sample Fuel Briquette

Fig. 3(b) XRD Pattern Of Coconut coir Sample Fuel Briquette-Matching Compounds

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) uses a focused beam of high-energy electrons to generate a variety of signals at the surface of solid specimens. The signals that derive from electron-sample interactions reveal information about the sample including external morphology (texture), chemical composition, and crystalline structure and orientation of materials making up the sample. In most applications, data are collected over a selected area of the surface of the sample, and a 2-dimensional image is generated that displays spatial variations in these properties. Areas ranging from approximately 1 cm to 5 microns in width can be imaged in a scanning mode using conventional SEM techniques (magnification ranging from 20X to approximately 30,000X, spatial resolution of 50 to 100 nm). The SEM is also capable of performing analyses of selected point locations on the sample; this approach is especially useful in qualitatively or semi-quantitatively determining chemical compositions (using EDS), crystalline structure, and crystal orientations (using EBSD). The design and function of the SEM is very similar to the EPMA and considerable overlap in capabilities exists between the two instruments.

SEM IMAGING

A Scanning Electron Microscope provides details surface information by tracing a sample in a raster pattern with an electron beam. The process begins with an electron gun generating a beam of energetic electrons down the column and onto a series of electromagnetic lenses. These lenses are tubes, wrapped in coil and referred to as solenoids. The coils are adjusted to focus the incident electron beam onto the sample; these adjustments cause fluctuations in the voltage, increasing/decreasing the speed in which the electrons come in contact with the specimen surface.

Controlled via computer, the SEM operator can adjust the beam to control magnification as well as determine the surface area to be scanned. The beam is focused onto the stage, where a solid sample is placed. Most samples require some preparation before being placed in the vacuum chamber.

Of the variety of different preparation processes, the two most commonly used prior to SEM analysis are sputter coating for non-conductive samples and dehydration of most biological specimens. In addition, all samples need to be able to handle the low pressure inside the vacuum chamber. The interaction between the incident electrons and the surface of the sample is determined by the acceleration rate of incident electrons, which carry significant amounts of kinetic energy before focused onto the sample. When the incident electrons come in contact with the sample, energetic electrons are released from the surface of the sample. The scatter patterns made by the interaction yields information on size, shape, texture and composition of the sample. A variety of detectors are used to attract different types of scattered electrons, including secondary and backscattered electrons as well as x-rays. Backscatter electrons are incidental electrons reflected backwards; images provide composition data related to element and compound detection. Although topographic information can be obtained using a backscatter detector, it is not as accurate as an SED. Diffracted backscatter electrons determine crystalline structures as well as the orientation of minerals and micro-fabrics.

X-rays, emitted from beneath the sample surface, can provide element and mineral information. SEM produces black and white, three-dimensional images. Image magnification can be up to 10 nanometers and, although it is not as powerful as its TEM counterpart, the intense interactions that take place on the surface of the specimen provide a greater depth of view, higher-resolution and, ultimately, a more detailed surface picture. SEMs have a variety of applications in a number of scientific and industry-related fields, especially where characterizations of solid materials is beneficial.

In addition to topographical, morphological and compositional information, a Scanning Electron Microscope can detect and analyze surface fractures, provide information in microstructures, examine surface contaminations, reveal spatial variations in chemical compositions, provide qualitative chemical analyses and identify crystalline structures. SEMs can be as essential research tool in fields such as life science, biology, gemology, medical and forensic science, metallurgy. In addition, SEMs have practical industrial and technological applications such as semiconductor inspection, production line of miniscule products and assembly of microchips for computers.

Her are the sem images of paper, rice husk and coconut coir are

Fig 4 (a) Electron Micrographs of Paper Sample Fuel Briquette with 200 mm

Fig 4 (b) Electron Micrographs Of paper Fuel Briquette With 500 μm

Fig 4 (c) Electron Micrographs Of Paper Fuel Briquette With 100μm

Fig 4 (d) Electron Micrographs Of Paper Fuel Briquette With Various Microns.

Morphological structure of paper samples are analysed at 2mm distance (21.2mm×25), 500um (25.0Kv 21.2mm×25), 100um (21.5mm×500), 25.0kv BSE 3D. The morphological structure of the paper showed lengthy cellulose like material. The particle size varying from 4.84 - 31.3um. The micro morphology of the briquette semi-coke produced at typical pyrolysis temperature under 3000 times magnification was shown in Fig. 5. At 400oC, it was due to the release of volatile, the pore structure formed in the semi-coke, and clear honeycomb-like pore structure distribution was shown in the local; at 600oC, the release of volatile increased, a larger size pore structure distribution appeared, while the small pore became the large pore, the cracks of large pore appeared; at 800oC, the large apparent melt pore appeared, the clear soft surface and the collapsed cracks structure formed.

Fig. 5 (a) Electron Micrographs Of Rice husk Sample Fuel Briquette With 200 mm

Fig 5 (b) Electron Micrographs Of Rice husk Fuel Briquette With 500 μm

Fig 5 (c) Electron Micrographs Of Rice husk Fuel Briquette With 100μm

Fig 5 (d) Electron Micrographs Of Rice husk Fuel Briquette With Various Microns.

Morphological structure of ricehusk samples are analysed at 2mm distance (21.2mm×25), 500um (25.0Kv 21.2mm×25), 100um (21.5mm×500), 25.0kv BSE 3D. The morphological structure of the ricehusk showed nonuniform short fibrous and coarser structure. The particle size is varying from to 3.76 to 21.0 μm. A possible explanation for the different mechanical properties showed by sawdust and olive stone could be the very different texture of both materials, as seen by SEM technique. Fig. 6 (a and b) show sawdust–coal and olive stone–coal char, respectively. Sawdust–coal char has a fibrous appearance due to the fibrous structure of the sawdust that remains after pyrolysis, whereas olive stone–coal char has a granular appearance. This typical fibrous texture of sawdust could favour the coal–biomass agglomeration [18].

Fig 6 (a) Electron Micrographs Of Coconut coir Sample Fuel Briquette With 200 mm

Fig 6 (b) Electron Micrographs Of Coconut coir Fuel Briquette With 500 μm

Fig 6 (c) Electron Micrographs Of Coconut coir Fuel Briquette With 100µm

Fig 6 (d) Electron Micrographs Of Coconut coir Briquette With Various Microns

Morphological structure of coconut coir samples are analysed at 2mm distance (21.2mm×25), 500um (25.0Kv 21.2mm×25), 100um (21.5mm×500), 25.0kv BSE 3D. The morphological structure of the coconut coir showed long fibrous and coarser structure. The particle size is varying from 5.05 to 41.6 µm. The micro-structural analyses (i.e., light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, and UV auto-fluorescence imaging) of corn stover and switchgrass briquettes and pellets showed that the natural binders in these biomass materials created “solid bridge” type bonding between particles in the briquettes and pellets. The potential natural binding components in these biomass materials are water soluble carbohydrates (2.2–7.9 % d.b.), lignin (8.8–9.2 % d.b.), protein (3.6–3.9 % d.b.), starch (0.4–1.0 % d.b.), and fat (0.7– 0.9 % d.b.).

PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

Effect of Moisture Content:

The moisture content of biomass is the quantity of water in the material, expressed as a percentage of the material's weight. This weight can be referred to on wet basis and on dry ash free basis. If the moisture content is determined on a ‘wet’ basis, the water's weight is expressed as a percentage of the sum of the weight of the water, ash, and dry-and-ash-free matter. Similarly, when calculating the moisture content on a ‘dry’ basis (however contradictory that may seem), the water’s weight is expressed as a percentage of the weight of the ash and dry-and-ash-free matter. Finally, the moisture content can be expressed as a percentage of the “dry and-ash-free” matter content. In that last case, the water's weight is related to the weight of the dry biomass. Because the moisture content affects the value of biomass as a fuel, the basis on which the moisture

content is measured must always be mentioned. This is particularly important because biomass materials exhibit a wide range of moisture content (on a wet basis), ranging from less than 10 percent for cereal grain straw up to 50 to 70 percent for forest residues .

Fig. 7. Effect of Moisture Content

The highest (mean ± SD) moisture content was witnessed in coconut coir is 59.00 followed by rice husk 58.75, paper 58.4. High percentage of moisture in biomass materials prevents their applications for thermo-chemical conversion processes including combustion similarly the water content has an influence on the net calorific value, the combustion efficiency and the temperature of combustion was noticed. Increasing biomass materials moisture content caused on decreasing the unit density of pellets considerably even at high applied pressures. The maximum pellet density of 1238.1 kg/m³ was observed at the moisture of 5% in a prickly lettuce, while it decreased to 926.5 kg/m³ in the moisture content of 20% [1].

Effect of Volatile matter: Volatile matter refers to the part of the biomass that is released when the biomass is heated (up to 400 to 500°C). During this heating process the biomass decomposes into volatile gases and solid char. Biomass typically has a high volatile matter content (up to 80 percent), whereas coal has a low volatile matter content (less than 20 percent) or, in the case of anthracite coal, a negligible one.

Fig. 8. Effect of Volatile matter

The highest (mean ± SD) volatile matter content was witnessed in paper i.e.10.3 followed by rice husk 9.8, coconut coir 5.75,. The higher proportion of volatiles results the major part of the biomass fuel being vaporised before homogeneous gas-phase combustion reactions take place. The remaining char undergoes heterogeneous combustion reactions. Char oxidation lasts considerably longer than the oxidation of combustible gases during the combustion process. The amount of volatile matter

therefore strongly influences the thermal decomposition and combustion behavior of solid fuels. Fuels with lower volatiles, or conversely a very high fixed carbon value, such as coal, need to be burnt on a grate as they take a long time to burn out if they are not pulverized to a very small size. A laboratory study of actual ash behavior from switch grass showed that elements such as K, S, B, Na, and Cu were volatilized from the ash at high temperatures [2] Elements such as Ca, Mg, P, Mn, Al, Fe and Si were retained even to high temperatures [3].

Effect of Ash content (%):

The inorganic component can be expressed as same as the moisture content on a wet, dry and ash free basis. In general it is expressed on dry basis. It is the inorganic matter left out after complete combustion of the biomass. Generally contains mainly Calcium, Potassium, Magnesium and Phosphorus elements that affect the ash fusion.

$$\text{ASH CONTENT (\%)} = ((W_2/W_1) \times 100)$$

Fig. 9 Effect of Ash content

The lowest (mean \pm SD) 10.3% of ash content obtained from the paper followed by rice husk 9.8%, coconut coir 5.75%. One particular problem that is encountered during thermal processes of biomass is the deposition and agglomeration caused from minerals in ash melts [4] stated: "Ash behaviour of agro-waste during thermochemical conversion is one of the most important matters to be studied". The minerals present with the feedstock, when subjected to high temperature and certain conditions, can agglomerate and deposit inside the thermal device leading to slag formation, fouling and bed agglomeration. Inorganic constituents, such as organically bound cations, inorganic salts and minerals make up the ash present in or on the surface of biomass [5]. Ashes are usually formed of CaO, K₂O, Na₂O, MgO, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, P₂O₅, SO₃ and Cl [6]. The ash content of agricultural waste affects its slagging behavior together with the operating temperature and mineral composition of ash.

Effect of Fixed carbon (%)

Carbon fixation is the conversion of inorganic carbon (carbon dioxide) to organic compounds by living organisms. Essentially, the fixed carbon of a fuel is the percentage of carbon available for char combustion. This is not equal to the total amount of carbon in the fuel (the ultimate carbon) because there is also a significant amount released as hydrocarbons in the volatiles. Fixed carbon gives an indication of the proportion of char that remains after the devolatilisation phase.

$$\text{Fixed Carbon by Difference} = 100 - (\text{Volatile Content} + \text{Ash Content} + \text{Moisture Content})$$

Fig. 10 Effect of Fixed carbon

The lowest (mean \pm SD) fixed carbon recorded in Rice Husk 17.9% followed by Paper 18.2%, Coconut coir 18.68%. The low fixed content making it tend to prolong cooking time by its low heat release (bake-oven effect) [7]. It also reduced the calorific energy of the briquettes by causing what is called fuel-saving effect. The higher the fixed carbon content the better the charcoal produced because the corresponding calorific energy is usually high (FAO, 1995).

Table 1.1

Proximate Analysis:

Quantity of paper sample takings, gms =150

Quantity of ricehusk sample taken, gms =112.4

Quantity of coconut coir sample taken, gms=173.2

Quantity of soaked water, lit =3

Time of soaking, hrs =24

Quantity of binder (plain flour) taken, gms =150

Temperature, k=296

Sl.no	Name of the sample	Moisture Content (%)	Ash Content (%)	Volatile matter (%)	Fixed Carbon (%)
1	Paper	15.32	10.3	58.4	18.2
2	Rice husk	16.82	9.8	58.75	17.9
3	Coconut coir	16.65	5.75	59.00	18.6

ULTIMATE ANALYSIS

Ultimate Analysis involves the estimation of important chemical elements that make up the biomass, namely carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur. The basic method for doing an ultimate analysis is to burn a sample of biomass in a platinum crucible in a stream of air to produce carbon dioxide and water, the mass fractions of which are determined by gas-analysis procedures (for example see [9] and the percentage of C and H calculated [10]. If the ash and moisture contents are known, the amount of oxygen can be determined by the difference.

The ultimate analysis or the determination of their percentage compositions were carried out using standard methods. Thus, ASTM D5373-02 method was used for the determination of percentage composition of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen, ASTM D4239-02 method was used for the determination of percentage composition of sulphur and ASTM D5142-02 method was used for the determination of percentage ash content of individual composite briquette samples. The percentage oxygen content of the individual composite agricultural waste briquette was determined by difference as

follows . (1) Where C, H,S, N ,O and Ash are the carbon, hydrogen, sulphur , nitrogen, oxygen and ash content of the composite agricultural waste briquettes respectively

ESTIMATION OF CARBON

The percentage of carbon in coconut coir briquette(52.012) is higher than paper briquette(51.12) and rice husk briquette(43.052).

Fig. 11 Estimation of percentge o carbon

ESTIMATION OF HYDROGEN

The percentage of hydrogen in coconut coir briquette (5.057) is higher than paper briquette (5.038) and ricehusk briquette(4.0357).

Fig. 12 Estimation of percentge of hydrogen

ESTIMATION OF NITROGEN

The percentage of nitrogen in paper briquette (1.9832) is higher than ricehusk briquette (1.1254) and coconut coir briquette(0.9200).

Fig. 13 Estimation of percentge of nitrogen

ESTIMATION OF SULPHUR

The percentage of sulphur in ricehusk briquette (0.254) is higher than paper briquette (0.203) and coconut coir briquette(0.172).

Fig. 14 Estimation of percentge of sulphur

ESTIMATION OF OXYGEN

The percentage of nitrogen in coconut coir briquette (52.067) is higher than paper briquette (49.8382) and ricehusk briquette(38.159).

Fig. 15 Estimation of percentge of oxygen

The composition of the Paper briquette analyzed as showed 51.12 % carbon, 5.038 % hydrogen, 49.8382 % oxygen, 1.9832 % nitrogen and 0.203 % sulphur. The results agree with the observations made by [8] who reported that analysis of biomass using the gas analysis procedures revealed the principal constituent as carbon, which comprises between 30% and 60% of the dry matter and typically 30% to 40% oxygen. Hydrogen, being the third main constituent, makes up between about 5% and 6%, and nitrogen and sulphur (and chlorine) normally make up less than 1% of dry biomass.

Fig. 16 The percentages of of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur

Name of the sample	%C	%H	%N ₂	%S	%O	Porosity(%)
Paper	51.12	5.038	1.983 2	0.20 3	49.838 2	77.77
Ricehusk	43.05 2	4.035 7	1.125 4	0.25 4	38.159	18.19
Coconut coir	52.01 2	5.057	0.920 0	0.17 2	52.067	42.78

Analysis of biomass using this method reveals the principal constituent as carbon, which comprises between 30 to 60 % of the dry matter. After that, typically 30 to 40 % is oxygen. Hydrogen is the third main constituent making up between about 5-6%. Typically nitrogen and sulphur (and chlorine) normally make up less than 1% of dry biomass [11]. The composition of a wide range of selected biomass fuels is given by Jenkins et al. [11]. Compared with other fuels (such as coal or peat), biomass contains relatively high amounts of oxygen and hydrogen [12]. The resulting composition of biomass affects its combustion characteristics. The total overall mass decrease in the fuel during the volatile combustion phase of the combustion is increased as the hydrogen to carbon ratio of the fuel increases, and, although to a lesser extent, as the oxygen to carbon ratio increases [11]. In terms of energy available in the fuel, one significant collection of natural fuels shows a linear correlation of the heat of combustion at 400°C with the carbon content of the analysis (cited in [13]). The high volatile content of biomass means it can lose over 90% of its mass in the devolatilisation stage of combustion, compared with coals which lose between 5 and 65% of their mass by this process.

APPARENT WATER ABSORPTION

Physical properties of wood pellets establish their quality. The physical properties that generally used to describe the integrity of the wood pellets are durability, bulk density, and porosity. The porosity of wood pellets, expressed in percentage, can be defined as the ratio of volume of voids to the total filled volume. The voids volume can be divided into (i) a major volume of voids existing among the pellets (outside) when they are held in bulk, and (ii) a minor volume corresponding to the collection of minute pores, cracks, and channels present inside pellet solids. The inclusion or exclusion of the pellet solids pore volume, further classifies porosity as total-porosity and apparent porosity (also known as bulk porosity/seed porosity/macro-porosity), respectively.

Fig. 17 The apparent water absorption of different fuel briquettes

Effect on Calorific Value:

The calorific value of Paper briquette is 4801 Kcal, Rice husk briquette is 3200 Kcal and Coconut coir is 4146 Kcal. From these values we found that paper briquette has more calorific value followed by coconut coir briquette and rice husk briquette. The computed calorific value for the sawdust charcoal briquette was 20,175.81 kJ/kg (4,820 kcal/kg). This energy value can produce enough heat required for household cooking and small-scale industrial cottage applications. The results of the calorific value of the charcoal briquettes compare well with the results of the heating value of sawdust briquette obtained by [16] and most biomass briquettes including almond shell briquette (19,490 kJ/kg) [14], corncob briquette (20,890 kJ/kg) [17], cowpea (14,372.93 kJ/kg) and soybeans (12,953 kJ/kg) [15].

DISCUSSIONS

Generally, briquettes of biomass materials show a lot of promise as a potential source of fuel. However, each biowaste material briquette requires different optimum conditions and subsequent work should concentrate on optimizing the fabrication processes for their industrial use.

- ❖ Energy and waste management policy initiatives should include recovery of organic by-products for Fuel briquette production. Based on this work an environmentally brick, with good commercial characteristics was made using recycling technology in a safe disposal manner for the studied pollutants.
- ❖ The technology has a great potential for converting waste biomass into a superior fuel for household use, in an affordable, efficient and environment friendly manner. Calorific value was found less in rice husk briquetted fuel as 3200 kcal. Maximum percentage of fixed carbon (18.68 %) was obtained from coconut coir where as in paper and ricehusk was 18.2 % and 17.9 % respectively. From this result Carbonized biomass was found suitable as compared to as such and hydrolyzed biomass for briquetted fuel.
- ❖ The recorded data can be aimed to project images of briquette production and consumption in organized systems and macro scale for the study area. Recycling biomass can be significantly alternative fuels. From this the research results can be applied to develop alternative fuels.

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